

Complex chemical mixtures: Approaches for assessing adverse human health effects

Ehab Mustafa, Maria João Valente and Anne Marie Vinggaard

Abstract

In this opinion, we provide a brief overview of three main approaches for assessing effects of chemical mixtures on human health, such as experimental or theoretical component-based or whole mixture studies. We compare the purposes, pros, and cons of the approaches and highlight the recent advances within the field that focus on “real-life” exposures for risk-assessing chemical mixtures. Whole mixture studies combined with effect-directed analysis have been used mostly within ecotoxicology and less so within human toxicology, opening the potential for the determination of mixture drivers in human tissues. Concerning the implementation of mixture risk assessment in legislation, we discuss whether a data-driven factor, for example, a mixture driver factor for each chemical or chemical class could be useful when deriving the toxicologically acceptable limit.

Addresses

Cell Toxicology Team, National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

Corresponding author: Vinggaard, Anne Marie (annv@food.dtu.dk)

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Keywords

Chemical mixture, Health risk assessment, Toxicology, Component-based studies, Whole mixture studies: Real-life exposure.

Introduction

Prediction of mixture effects of chemicals is attainable in most cases if valid data are available. However, one of the bottlenecks of mixture risk assessment (MRA) is the availability of valid and robust hazard and exposure data for a large number of chemicals. Hazard data are the same for each chemical whether the purpose is to assess the risk to a single chemical or a chemical mixture.

However, for exposure data, there is a wish or a requirement to know about co-exposure of the chemicals. This is a challenge as knowledge about “real-life exposures”, that is, which chemicals occur in the same place at the same time, and in what concentrations, is scarce and scattered. Human exposure is complex since real-life exposure patterns are dependent on temporal (i.e., time of the day, year, and season) and geographical (countryside and urban areas) variations in exposure and are determined to a large extent by dietary habits, individual use of personal care products, inhalation of dust, external environment, and so on. In other words, each person has his/her own individual exposure pattern that changes over time.

In cases where co-exposure is evident and many chemicals have been measured in the same individual, it is possible to calculate the mixture risk to certain adverse effects as it has been done recently for mixture effects on sperm quality [1] or for human breast milk contaminants on neurodevelopmental and thyroid effects in infants [2].

How do we deal with such complexity when attempting to regulate chemicals to protect an entire population, such as the European population? In this opinion, we look backward and provide a brief overview of three main approaches for studying chemical mixture effects and predicting risks entailed by mixture exposure (as illustrated in [Figure 1](#)), and, finally, we discuss the way forward for implementing MRA.

Component-based approaches on “artificial” chemical mixtures

We use the term “artificial” chemical mixtures for mixtures in which all chemicals are added at a concentration relative to their potency (e.g., their EC₅₀ or no observed adverse effect levels). Because of this equipotency, they have also been termed “balanced” chemical mixtures [3]. Component-based experimental studies, designed to determine potential interactions between compounds with the same target, indicate that these chemicals mainly act additively at low dose levels ([Figure 1a](#)) [4]. Only in rare cases, synergy and antagonism occur [5]. This means that it is possible to predict the mixture effect by mathematical modeling following the concentration addition principle, where the safety of

Figure 1

	COMPONENT-BASED MIXTURE STUDIES		WHOLE MIXTURE STUDIES		
	A 'ARTIFICIAL' CHEMICAL MIXTURES		B RECONSTITUTED MIXTURES BASED ON 'REAL-LIFE' EXPOSURES		
	C EXTRACTS OF 'REAL-LIFE' EXPOSURES				
	BALANCED MIXTURES		NON-BALANCED MIXTURES		
	EXPERIMENTAL		EXPERIMENTAL	THEORETICAL CASE STUDIES	EXPERIMENTAL
PURPOSE	To determine whether chemicals in a balance mixture interact or not	To determine whether chemicals at low concentrations/doses contribute to the mixture effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To determine whether a 'real-life' mixture from the environment-food-human continuum will cause a hazard or a risk To determine whether chemicals in an unbalanced mixture interact or not 		To determine whether a 'real-life' mixture from a specific sample from the environment-food-human continuum will cause a specific hazard
STARTING POINT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of a specific (adverse) effect • Which chemical mixture? • Which effect(s) to address? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of a specific (adverse) effect • Selection of model compound(s) exhibiting this effect and determination of the NOAELs or LOECs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human biomonitoring data for chemical exposure • A specific (adverse) effect 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A specific (adverse) effect • A chemical extract from the environment, food, or human tissue
DATA TREATMENT AND OUTCOMES	To highlight additivity or deviation from additivity (synergism or antagonism)	Observation of a mixture effect	Observation of a mixture effect and/or estimation of risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calculation of a risk • Use of relative potency factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An integrated mixture effect • Effect-based trigger values
MAIN CONCLUSIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For similarly or dissimilarly acting compounds, mainly CA is observed • Only synergism in rare cases at low, realistic human exposure levels • CA and IA often produce similar predictions 	'Something from nothing': Chemicals contribute to mixture effects at low concentrations	Evidence that chemical mixtures may pose a risk to human health for certain population segments		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In vitro models that can be used to assess risks from exposure to 'real-life' mixtures in human and environmental samples • Effect-based trigger values
EXAMPLES OF REFERENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kortenkamp et al. 2009 [4] • EFSA Report 2013 [22] • Howdeshell et al. 2017 [23] • Martin et al. 2021 [5] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Silva et al. 2002 [8] • Hass et al. 2007 [6] • Van Der Ven et al. 2022 [7] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evans et al. 2012 [3] • Hadrup et al. 2016 [11] • Berntsen et al. 2017 [10] • Ahmed et al. 2019 [9] • Caporale et al. 2022 [13] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loy et al. 2015 [24] • Kortenkamp et al. 2021 [14] • Kortenkamp et al. 2022 [1] • Bil et al. 2023 [25] • Ma et al. 2023 [16] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Escher et al. 2018 [26] • Rodriguez-Carrillo et al. 2021 [18] • Tralau et al. 2021 [27] • Vinggaard et al. 2021 [17] • Escher et al. 2022 [19]

NOAEL: No Observed Adverse Effect Level; LOEC: Lowest Observed Effect Concentration; CA: Concentration Addition; IA: Independent Action

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An overview of experimental and theoretical approaches used to perform hazard and/or risk assessment of chemical mixtures. References cited in the figure [1,3–11,13,14,16–19,22–27].

the mixture for human health is expressed as the sum of the risk quotients of all compounds considered, whereby values < 1 imply sufficient protection. In this approach, it is assumed that aggregate effects can be characterized by each single chemical based on their toxic potency and their concentration in the mixture [4]. This principle is valid for similarly acting chemicals, but evidence has arisen that it also applies to dissimilarly acting chemicals [6,7]. As it is impossible to test every imaginable chemical mixture, this assumption is crucial for MRA because it implies that the mixture effect can be predicted based on hazard and exposure data of single chemicals with a certain level of confidence.

Yet, another application of component-based mixture studies has been to study whether low, realistic, and even non-detectable levels of chemicals could contribute to a mixture effect (Figure 1a, second column). This led to the phenomenon popularly called "something from nothing," which showed that even small concentrations of chemicals could add up to a measurable mixture effect. Such observations are a direct consequence of chemicals acting additively, where the mixture effect observed is caused by the very low (and often not measurable) concentrations of the

chemicals in the mixture that are "located" at the flat bottom part of the sigmoidal concentration-response curves, which add up to a measurable mixture effect at the linear part of the concentration-response curve. This was shown for estrogen receptor activation by chemicals of environmental relevance [8], male rat pups exposed to antiandrogen mixtures during gestation [6], and recently craniofacial malformations in zebrafish exposed to a mixture of chemicals with dissimilar modes of action [7].

Component-based approaches on reconstituted "real-life" chemical mixtures Experimental studies

Reconstituted chemical mixtures can be based on, for example, human biomonitoring or food intake data to better reflect actual human exposure levels (Figure 1b). Each chemical is present in a so-called "non-balanced" mixture [3] according to its actual concentration in the blood, urine, or food, as well as not according to its potency. This means that one or a few chemicals can dominate in exerting the adverse effect. Mixtures of larger numbers of chemicals defined from human biomonitoring data have been studied in animals or cell cultures. They have indicated that the current human

exposure to mixtures may leave a pathological or pathophysiological footprint, potentially affecting human health [3,9–12].

A novel and elegant approach to MRA was taken by Caporale *et al.*, 2022, who focused on language delay as a marker for neurodevelopmental adverse effects, as it predicts later educational achievements [13]. Based on a pre-defined evaluation matrix, 15 parent compounds known to be endocrine-disrupting compounds (EDCs) were selected and measured in pregnant women from the SELMA cohort, and a mixture of 8 of these (namely, bisphenol A, four phthalates, and three per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances) was identified to contribute to the association with language delay. Based on the proportions of these chemicals found in the mothers, a reconstituted “real-life” mixture was designed and tested both *in vitro* in two human stem cell-based models and *in vivo* in *X. laevis* and zebrafish larvae. The mechanistic *in vitro* studies showed that the mixture interfered with hormonal pathways and dysregulated biological pathways that are causally linked to language delay. While the *in vivo* studies confirmed thyroid function as a key and unifying point of vulnerability to the mixture and correlated thyroid disruption to neurodevelopmental adverse effects assessed as altered locomotor activity. From these experiments, points of departure (PODs) were estimated to be used for MRA. The epidemiological and experimental evidence was integrated for MRA, showing that >90% of the pregnant women had exposure levels sufficiently similar to the reference mixture. Similarly to a risk or hazard quotient commonly used for single chemicals, a similar mixture risk indicator (SMRI) was calculated for these women, dividing individual exposure levels by the estimated PODs. Among the women with similar exposure profiles, 54% had a calculated SMRI >1. Furthermore, 2.5-year-old children with maternal prenatal levels sufficiently similar to the mixture with the highest SMRIs were 3.3 times more likely to have language delay than those having the lowest SMRIs. The limitation of this study is that the focus was directed toward predetermined EDCs and that the study required many resources. Still, this is an elegant example of how to integrate *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and epidemiological data to perform a MRA that may serve as an inspiration for future evaluations of human risk to chemical mixtures.

Theoretical studies based on available hazard and exposure levels

Several component-based theoretical case studies (Figure 1b, second column) have been performed under the European H2020 joint program Human Biomonitoring for Europe (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>). In these studies, human mixture risk was predicted based on existing, aggregated human exposure levels and hazard information obtained from either *in vivo* or *in vitro* data [14].

As a starting point, one can use chemicals that share a common mechanism of action [15]. This was done recently for chemicals exhibiting androgen receptor antagonism (hAR) *in vitro*, which is the major and well-known molecular initiating event for male reproductive health disorders [16]. We explored an approach for chemical MRA based on human *in vitro* data combined with aggregated human exposure data, thereby circumventing the drawbacks of using hazard data from rodents and estimated exposure intake levels. Our work identified 231 chemicals able to interfere with hAR activity. Among them, 61 were finally identified as having both reliable hAR antagonist and human biomonitoring data. Calculation of risk quotients indicated that the mixture drivers were certain PCBs, phthalates, perfluorooctanesulfonic acid, and benzophenone-3. The approach is still encumbered with uncertainties mainly related to *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolations, but it shows the great future potential for MRA following refinement.

In another recent mixture study, the starting point was individual co-exposures to 29 chemicals in 98 young men. These exposure data were combined with available sperm quality data from rodents to estimate the human risk and construct personalized hazard indices [1]. The exceedances of “acceptable” mixture exposures were determined for each subject. It was found that tolerable combined exposures to chemicals associated with reduced semen quality were exceeded by a large margin and that bisphenols, polychlorinated dioxins, phthalates, and analgesics drive these risks.

Another recent study used chemical profiles of human breast milk as the starting point [2]. Typical mixture profiles were identified, and mixture risk was calculated for every individual by using hazard data from the literature, and it turned out that DDTs, PCBs, and arsenic were the major chemical mixture drivers for neurotoxicity.

Whole mixture approaches

The third approach for mixture assessments is based on whole mixture studies on real-life exposures (Figure 1c). With the term whole mixtures, we mean complex chemical mixtures that are extracted from, for example, environmental (water, soil, and air), food (food basket or single food items), or human samples (blood, urine, milk, placenta, etc.). Such mixtures closely reflect a composition of chemicals that are present in the food that we eat or are present in human tissues.

Whole mixture studies have most often been performed on environmental samples, but a recent review reported on 43 whole mixture studies performed on human tissues [17]. Receptor-based *in vitro* activity assessments (*e.g.*, AhR, ER, and AR assays) were found to be useful in epidemiological studies to measure a combined and integrated effect of actual chemical mixtures present in

human tissue, taking additive or potential interactions into consideration [17,18]. The outcome provides a comprehensive picture of the combined effect exerted by a mixture of known and unknown chemicals of emerging concern, thus advancing our knowledge toward a more real-life scenario. This approach can direct our attention to so far unattended chemicals of emerging concern in cases where the goal is to identify mixture drivers in the tissue/sample. The *in vitro* endpoint may serve either as a biomarker of mixture effect when it correlates with a specific disease outcome and/or as a biomarker of mixed exposure when associating with a population's demographic characteristics or dietary profiles (Figure 2).

The combination of whole mixture studies with effect-directed analysis (EDA) makes it possible to identify chemical mixture drivers in a more unblinded manner. In the Green Deal project PANORAMIX (<https://panoramix-h2020.eu/>), whole mixture studies are performed on chemical extracts from the environment-food-human continuum in order to determine and compare the chemical mixture drivers when we move up along the food chain [19]. Combining *in vitro* bioassays with advanced high-resolution analytical tools for suspect and non-target screening can be seen as an

advantageous way forward to direct human exposure analysis to chemical mixtures that are potentially hazardous and of concern. Applying EDA to human exposure has been very limited, as it has often been used to investigate environmental samples. Thus, a huge field of novel applications waits for exploration and practical application in epidemiological studies, which could lead to a paradigm shift in exposure and biomarker research.

How can MRA be implemented in legislation?

It is a challenge to reach consensus on how to implement mixture risks in legislation in order to safeguard human health. Given the complexity of MRA and the potential human health risk not accounted for, we propose a pragmatic approach that requires an acceptance of uncertainties in assessing and managing risk to chemical mixtures. First, we need to reduce complexity by accepting that rare cases of synergism and antagonism will not be accounted for, and by realizing that knowledge on individual co-exposures of chemicals, at specific points in time, is useful to qualify our knowledge on human mixture risks but is a challenge to incorporate into regulatory risk assessment and management measures to protect an entire population. Instead, we suggest an improved MRA based on

Figure 2

Whole mixtures extracted from healthy or diseased individuals that reflect actual human exposure are analyzed *in vitro*, for example, for aryl hydrocarbon activity (AhR), antiandrogenic activity (AR), estrogen activity (ER), or genotoxicity. The purpose is to correlate the specific adverse effect to disease outcomes (biomarkers of effect) or demographic characteristics, pollution sources, or dietary habits (biomarkers of exposure). Effect-directed analysis (EDA) can eventually be applied to identify chemical mixture drivers. Modified from Vinggaard et al., 2021 [17*].

improvements in the risk assessment of single chemicals. One of the challenges of legislation is that chemical classes are regulated in regulatory silos, each covering a specific group of chemicals, whereas chemical mixtures in real-life work across silos. Therefore, the application of a mixture allocation factor (MAF) to account for mixture effects in legislation is being discussed at ECHA in relation to the European Regulation REACH. The suggestion is to apply a MAF of 5 to all chemicals that are produced above a certain tonnage limit (*personal communication*) in order to take mixture risk into account. This factor is a default factor, which is not driven by data on the specific chemical, but is rather a general factor in line with uncertainty factors (*e.g.* 10 for interindividual differences and 10 for interspecies differences).

An alternative way forward could be to qualify and derive a more data-driven and science-based factor for each chemical that could be included in the risk assessment of each single chemical. One could imagine the assignment of a “mixture driver factor” (MDF, *e.g.*, from 1 to 10) for each chemical for each adverse toxicological effect based on current knowledge. Based on present and future MRAs, the chemicals that drive the specific mixture effect in question have been or will be determined. The underlying studies could be theoretical case studies and/or experimental mixture studies based on reconstituted or whole mixture assessments involving EDA as those described above (Figures 1b and 1c). Chemicals that contribute to the mixture effect above a certain percentage should have assigned a MDF for the specific adverse effect. The risk assessment of a specific chemical could then consider the magnitude and the number of MDFs to derive a final tolerable intake or acceptable exposure level for humans. The idea is not fully developed and needs further consideration/research before it is possible to validate its potential.

As an example, MRAs of chemicals affecting male reproductive health could be mentioned [1,16,20]. From these studies, we have indications that the chemicals driving the mixture effect include bisphenols, phthalates, paracetamol, PCBs, dioxins, benzophenone-3, perfluorooctanesulfonic acid, methylparaben, triclosan, and certain pesticides. Some deviations between studies’ outcomes exist, and we must be pragmatic and acknowledge this, as different methodologies were used. Still, based on such studies, a MDF for reproductive toxicity could be assigned to the main mixture drivers. These factors should be dynamic and potentially subject to change when new information appears in the future. For developmental neurotoxicity, similar MDFs could be derived, for example, based on [13] and other studies. Interindividual variation of chemical mixture drivers adds up to the challenges of MRA, as they may change over time and space depending on the exact exposures.

Therefore, MRAs of various study populations may lead to the identification of different chemical mixture drivers. Consequently, aggregated exposures for large population segments could be used in the MRAs to obtain exposure measures that, for pragmatic purposes, may estimate the exposure of “an average European person.” Again, we have to accept the uncertainties that this will introduce. In the future, we may realize that the problematic chemicals that generally drive the mixture risks often include chemicals for which we have indications that current human exposure levels are exerting a risk for some population segments and also for *single* chemicals (*e.g.*, PCBs, per-fluoroalkyl substances, phthalates, and bisphenol A). Moreover, specific chemicals will probably be mixture drivers for not just one, but more adverse outcomes. Such conditions may contribute to lowering the complexity of setting the MDF.

A key limitation of current MRA is the shortage of available information on many single chemicals regarding human exposure levels and/or toxicity data. So far, only a minor fraction of the many thousands of chemicals in current use have had allocated a measure of threshold toxicity. MRAs can improve when these matters are solved, namely both single-chemical exposure and hazard data, as well as improved methods to cover aggregate exposures [21]. This is among other things the focus of the ongoing Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) initiative and the work on the Integrated Chemical Environment (ICE) platform by the National Toxicology Program (NTP) in the USA.

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Given her role as Guest Editor, Anne Marie Vinggaard had no involvement in the peer-review of this article and has no access to information regarding its peer-review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to Andreas Kortenkamp.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

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* of special interest

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